

Coumarin Derivatives. Part I: Synthesis and Screening of Some New Nitrones of 4-Formyl-7-methoxy-, and 3-Formyl/Acetyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarins

D. R. SHRIDHAR*, L. C. VISHWAKARMA, O. P. BANSAL, R. S. PRASAD and B. LAL

Research & Development Department, Indian Drugs & Pharmaceuticals Limited, Hyderabad—500 037

Manuscript received 6 March 1978, revised 9 June 1978, accepted 7 July 1978

In a continued search for new antimicrobial agents some new nitrones of 4-formyl-7-methoxy- and 3-formyl/acetyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarins have been synthesised by condensing the respective formylcoumarins with appropriate N-alkyl/aryl hydroxylamines. The structures of these nitrones were established on the basis of their elemental analyses and spectral (IR & NMR) data. All the new nitrones thus prepared, have been screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial, antimycobacterial, antifungal, anti-amoebic and *in vivo* anthelmintic properties.

SEVERAL coumarin derivatives have been reported to possess antibacterial¹, antifungal² and other biological³ properties. Recently N-alkyl/aryl nitrones derived from some heteroaromatic systems^{4,5} have been described as bactericides, fungicides and antiprotozoal agents. A recent report⁶ from our laboratory described the synthesis and antibacterial activity of some 4-[2-(heteroaryl)]vinyl coumarins. In continuation of this work, a series of new nitrones of 4-formyl-7-methoxy- and 3-formyl/acetyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarins of type I and II respectively has been synthesised with a view to study their antimicrobial and antiparasitic activities. The synthesis and screening results of these nitrones are reported in the present paper.

The intermediates 4-formyl-7-methoxy-⁷ and 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarins⁸ were prepared according to the known methods. The hitherto unreported 3-formyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin was prepared by condensing the corresponding coumarin with triethylorthoformate followed by the hydrolysis of the resulting *tris* coumarin with aqueous sodium acetate solution according to the method of Checchi et al⁹. The N-alkyl/aryl hydroxylamines were prepared by the known methods¹⁰.

The desired nitrones (I & II) were prepared by the condensation of the above-mentioned formyl/acetylcoumarins with various N-alkyl/arylhydroxylamines in ethanol in presence of acetic acid. All nitrones of 4-formyl-7-methoxy- and N-alkyl-nitrones of 3-formyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarins were thus formed readily at room temperature whereas in the case of other nitrones the reaction mixture had to be heated under reflux for 2-8 hr. for the completion of the reaction. The various coumarin-4-nitrones (Structure I) were obtained in 50-80%

yield while the 3-nitrones (Structure II) in 20-50% yield as pale yellow to dark yellow crystalline solids after recrystallizing from a suitable solvent. The purity and homogeneity were checked by tlc and characterisation done by their elemental analyses and IR measurements which showed characteristic absorption peaks¹¹ at 1610-1620 cm⁻¹(C=N), 1260-1270 cm⁻¹(N→O), 1145-1185 cm⁻¹(C-N) and 1690-1710 cm⁻¹(lactone C=O). The NMR spectra of some representative compounds (I-1, 3 & 9 and II-3) were consistent with the assigned structures. All the compounds thus synthesised are listed under general structures I and II.

All the compounds were subjected to *in vitro* antibacterial, antifungal, anti-amoebic and *in vivo* anthelmintic screening.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. Micro-analyses were performed using the Hosli Micro-combustion apparatus M K 101. All the compounds were analysed for C, H & N and the analytical results are within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the theoretical values. IR spectra were taken in KBr or nujol mull on a Perkin-Elmer-237 Grating IR spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian A-90 instrument in trifluoroacetic acid with TMS as internal standard.

Preparation of α -4-(7-Methoxycoumarinyl)-N-Methyl Nitron (I-1)

To a solution of 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin⁷ (6.12 g, 0.03 mole) in ethanol (500 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (2 ml) was added dropwise with stirring a solution of N-methylhydroxylamine

(I)

(II)

No	R	M.P. (°C)
1	CH ₃	225-226
2	C ₂ H ₅	202-203
3	n-C ₃ H ₇	185-186
4	iso-C ₃ H ₇	223-224
5	n-C ₄ H ₉	172-173
6	CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	210-212
7	CH ₂ CH ₂ OH	195-196
8	C ₆ H ₁₁	210-211
9	C ₆ H ₅	223-224
10	p-ClC ₆ H ₄	226-227

No	R	R ₁	M.P. (°C)
1	H	CH ₃	230-231
2	H	C ₂ H ₅	176-177
3	H	n-C ₃ H ₇	152-153
4	H	iso-C ₃ H ₇	123-125
5	H	n-C ₄ H ₉	130-131
6	H	iso-C ₄ H ₉	143-144
7	H	sec-C ₄ H ₉	109-110
8	H	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	220-221
9	H	CH ₂ CH ₂ OH	186-188
10	H	C ₆ H ₁₁	159-160
11	H	C ₆ H ₅	192-194
12	H	p-ClC ₆ H ₄	160-161
13	H	o-ClC ₆ H ₄	150-151
14	H	o-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	200-201
15	OH	CH ₃	144-145
16	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	96-97
17	CH ₃	n-C ₃ H ₇	85-86
18	CH ₃	iso-C ₃ H ₇	119-120
19	CH ₃	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	137-138
20	CH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₂ OH	117-118
21	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	170-171

All the above compounds were satisfactorily analysed for C, H & N.

(2.35 g, 0.05 mole) in water (30 ml). A yellow crystalline product started separating out after a few minutes. The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for 2 hr. The solvent was completely removed under reduced pressure and the residual solid was taken in water (100 ml), filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from DMF-ethanol to give golden yellow shining plates.

ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1690 (lactone C=O), 1625(C=N), 1270(N→O)

and 1145 (C-N) cm^{-1} ; NMR: δ 3.98 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 4.28 (s, 3H, N-CH₃), 7.0-7.25 (m, 2H, H₆ & H₈), 7.65 (d, J_{6,8} = 9 Hz, 1H, H₆), 7.78 (s, 1H, H₈) & 8.50 (s, 1H, CH=N).

All the other nitrones reported under structure I were prepared similarly using ethanolic solution of N-alkyl/arylhydroxylamines.

3-Formyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin

A suspension of 4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin¹⁸ (25 g, 0.13 mole) in triethylorthoformate (150 ml) was heated under reflux in an oil bath at 110° for 1 hr. with stirring. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into water (1.5 lit.) and stirred for 2 hr. The resulting *tris* coumarin was collected by filtration and dried. To this dry *tris* coumarin (25 g, 0.042 mole) a solution of anhydrous sodium acetate (7.5 g, 0.088 mole) in water (750 ml) was added and the mixture was heated on a water bath for 2 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate was acidified to congo red with conc. HCl when the 3-formyl derivative precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with cold water, dried and recrystallised from DMF to give 3g (34%) of pure 3-

formyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin, m.p. 213-215° (Found: C, 60.01; H, 3.64, C₁₁H₈O₅ requires C, 59.67; H, 3.41%); $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1725 cm^{-1} (lactone C=O) and 1620-1650 cm^{-1} (broad, H-bonded CHO group). It was used for further reactions immediately as it was found to be unstable on long storing.

Preparation of α -3-(4-Hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarinyl)-N-n-Propyl Nitron (II-3).

To a clear solution of 3-formyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin (11.0 g, 0.05 mole) in hot ethanol (300 ml) was added dropwise with stirring a solution of N-n-propylhydroxylamine (6.0 g, 0.08 mole) in ethanol (20 ml). The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for 10 hr. Solvent was completely removed under reduced pressure and the residual solid was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to give light yellow needles.

$\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1695 (lactone C=O), 1610 (C=N), 1280 (N→O) and 1150 (C-N) cm^{-1} ; NMR: δ 1.15 (t, J=6 Hz, 3H, CH₃), 2.1 (q, J=6 Hz, 2H, CH₂), 4.05 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 4.15 (t, 2H, J=9 Hz, N-CH₂), 7.0-7.25 (m, 2H, H₆ & H₈), 8.05 (d, J_{6,8} = 9Hz, H₆) and 8.45 (s, 1H, CH=N).

All the nitrones of 3-formyl/acetyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin reported under structure II were prepared in a similar manner.

Results and Discussion (Biological Screening)

All compounds were tested for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity by serial dilution tube method

and antifungal activity by agar dilution assay method as described earlier¹³. The highest dilution of the test compound which inhibited the visual growth of the organism was taken as the minimum inhibitory concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$). The bacteria employed were *S. aureus*, *S. faecalis*, *E. coli*, *Ps. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumoniae*, *S. typhi*, *A. tumefaciens*, *P. vulgaris*, *V. cholerae*, *S. dysenteriae* and *M. tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv and the fungi used were *T. mentagrophytes*, *T. rubrum*, *M. canis*, *M. gypseum*, *C. albicans*, *Cr. neoformans*, *A. fumigatus*, *H. capsulatum*, *S. schenckii* and *E. floccosum*. The *in vitro* anti-amoebic activity of the compounds against *E. histolytica* was determined by standard procedure¹⁴. The compounds were also screened for *in vivo* anthelmintic activity¹⁵ against *N. dubius* in rats.

The *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activities of all compounds were insignificant although two nitrones of 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (I-9 & 10) and eleven nitrones of 3-formyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin (II-1-3, 5, 7-9 & 11-14) were found to be moderately active against *M. tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv at 50-200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Amongst the nitrones of 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin, only N-propyl derivative (II-17) showed widest albeit low *in vitro* antifungal activity by inhibiting the growth of *T. mentagrophytes*, *T. rubrum*, *M. canis*, *M. gypseum*, *E. floccosum* and *H. capsulatum* at a range of 100-200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, while the remaining were devoid of antibacterial or antifungal activities.

Five nitrones of 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (I-2, 3, 7, 9 and 10) and two nitrones of 3-formyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin (II-7 & 9) exhibited appreciable *in vitro* anti-amoebic activity against *E. histolytica* at 62.5-250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ but was not significant enough to proceed with for *in vivo* screening. None of these nitrones showed any promising anthelmintic activity against *N. dubius* when tested in rats.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. G. S. Reddi, Dr. K. K. Bhopale and staff of Biology Division of this department for biological screening and Mr. A. K. S. Bhujanga Rao for technical assistance. Thanks are also due to the staff of our analytical laboratories for elemental analyses and spectral data.

References

- (a) T. UKITE, D. MIZUNO, T. TAMURA, T. YAMAKAWA and S. NOJIMA, *J. Pharm. Soc. (Japan)*, 1951, **71**, 2384; (b) T. TODA, T. TOKONAGA, T. OUCHIDA, K. SHIROGS and T. NAKMOTO, *Chemother. (Tokyo)*, 1958, **6**, 91; *Chem. Abs.* 1958, **52**, 203888.
- D. P. CHAKRABORTY, A. DASGUPTA and P. K. BOSE, *Ann. Biochem. & Exp. Med.*, 1957, **17**, 59; *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, **52**, 1352.
- H. K. BOITZE, P. R. SEIDEL, H. JACOBI and H. D. DELL, *Ger. Pat.* 2, 448, 257 (1976); *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, **85**, p32846b.
- Dainippon Pharmaceutical Co. Ltd., *Brit. Pat.* 1,105,007 (1968); *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, **69**, p86810.
- M. L. EDWARDS, R. E. BAMBURY and H. W. RITTER, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1975, **18**, 637.
- D. R. SHRIDHAR, C. V. REDDY SASTRY, S. R. MOORTY and N. K. VAIDYA, *Indian Pat.* 141903 (1977).
- A. SCHIAVELLO and E. CINGOLANI, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1951, **81**, 717; *Chem. Abs.* 1952, **46**, 6126d.
- (a) G. C. BADCOCK, F. M. DEAN, A. ROBERTSON and W. B. WHALLEY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 903. (b) H. R. EISENHAUER and K. P. LINK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2044.
- S. CHECCHI, L. P. VETTORI and G. RENZI, *Farmaco, Ed. Sci.*, 1969, **24**(6), 630; *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, **71**, 61132g.
- (a) "Practical Organic Chemistry" by A. I. VOGEL, London, 1971, p. 629; (b) O. KAMM, "Organic Synthesis", Coll. Vol. 1, (Ed.) H. GILMAN, JOHN WILEY & SONS, Inc., New York, 1964, p. 445. (c) E. BAMBERGER and F. L. PYMAN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 2297; (d) R. D. HAWORTH and A. LAPWORTH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **120**, 768; (e) H. FRUER, B. F. VINCENT JR., and R. S. BARTLETT, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, **30**, 2877; (f) G. ZINNER, *Archiv. Pharm.* 1963, **296**, 57; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, **59**, 486e; (g) G. ZINNER, *Archiv. Pharm.* 1963, **296**, 420; *Chem. Abs.* 1965, **63**, 600e. (h) S. R. SANDLER and W. KARO, "Organic Functional Group Preparations", (Ed.) A. T. BLOMQUIST and H. WASSERMAN, Academic Press (New York), 1972, Vol. 12-III, p. 337.
- (a) J. HAMER and A. MACALUSO, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, **64**, 475; (b) P. A. S. SMITH and J. E. ROBERTSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 1197; (c) G. KAMAI, A. D. NIKOLAEVA and U. S. PEREKHODKO, *Zh. Org. Khim.*, 1969, **5**(2), 244; *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, **70**, 105901t.
- J. BOYD and A. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 174.
- (a) D. R. SHRIDHAR, C. V. REDDY SASTRY, N. K. VAIDYA, G. S. REDDI and G. S. THAPAR, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1976, **65**(7), 1074. (b) D. R. SHRIDHAR, C. V. REDDY SASTRY, S. R. MOORTY, N. K. VAIDYA, P. G. REDDY, G. S. REDDI and G. S. THAPAR, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1977, **20**, 149.
- (a) S. R. DAS, U. SAXENA and P. N. SINGH, *Ann. Biochem. & Expt. Med.*, 1963, **23**, 57; (b) J. S. STEWARD, *Parasitology*, 1955, **45**, 281.
- G. BRODY and T. E. ELWARD, *J. Parasitology*, 1971, **57**, 1068.